

PROFESSIONAL STRESS OF GENERAL PRACTITIONERS AND ITS CAUSES

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Abstract: The article provides an analysis of the scientific literature on the concept of "professional stress" and the reason for its occurrence in the activities of a general practitioner, indicating the need for further research in this area. The causes of professional stress in the activities of a general practitioner are widely covered. Identification of the causes of professional stress in the activities of a general practitioner can become the basis for the development of additional criteria for its prevention.

The purpose of the work: to identify the concept of "professional stress" and the reasons for its occurrence in the activities of a general practitioner.

Conclusion. Thus, based on the foregoing, it seems appropriate to conclude that today, despite the lack of a unified definition of the concept under study, its active use in various studies is observed. Occupational stress is considered as the main generic concept that generalizes a fairly wide range of terms: work stress; work stress; work stress; organizational stress, etc.

Key words: general practitioner, occupational stress, stressor, stress resistance,

Today in our Republic there is an active improvement of the health care system, where a special place is occupied by the development of primary health care based on the principles of general (family) practice. At the center of this process are doctors, on whom the effectiveness of this area as a whole largely depends. The most important characteristics of the professional activity of these specialists are tension, increased responsibility for the decisions made, their consequences, the presence of a wide range of duties, saturation with a variety of communicative situations with patients, their family members, which are distinguished by their non-standard and, as a rule, emotional background. In addition, the complexity and specificity of the professional tasks that are being solved today by general practitioners in the field, as well as constant socio-economic changes, cause a significant intensification of their professional activities.

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In modern psychological literature, several terms are used that are close to the concept under study: work stress, organizational stress, etc. Work stress occurs as a result of complications associated with the work environment, i.e. production factors, which are overwhelmingly generated by civilization and scientific and technological progress. The modern professional environment, which is artificially created, is very different from the natural (natural) environment that a person needs as a biological being, and sometimes causes many problems, among which are the difficulties associated with: the content of the

work; with means of work, with physical-chemical and technical conditions of work [4,6,19,30].

In turn, occupational stress is most often understood as such a negative mental state, which is caused by the characteristics and requirements of the profession itself. Among the main causes of such stress, complications can be distinguished: those arising in the performance of functional duties by the subject of professional activity, due to the specifics of the corresponding profession; due to the low level of satisfaction of the needs and motives of the subject of professional activity; arising in the absence of a role balance between the professional sphere and the personal sphere, i.e. role overload, role deficiency, unclear role definition, role conflicts, etc. [20,30].

V.A. Bodrov argues that when considering occupational stress, it is necessary to take into account the general understanding of the problem of stress, which is being studied in modern science by representatives of various schools and trends. [5].

A.V. Pavlova notes that the problem of occupational stress as a separate area has been especially intensively developed in psychological science in the last two decades. This is due to the fact that the negative impact of this phenomenon on the level of efficiency of professional activity and the state of health of specialists was clarified. As a rule, in these studies we are talking about mental overload, psychosomatic disorders, negative behavioral reactions that arose as a result of the influence of occupational stressors in specialists of various types of professions.

In the literature on the problem of occupational stress, one can find information about the great importance of studying this problem for the economies of many countries. Since the costs of organizations for the medical care of staff reach an impressive size. This fact significantly stimulates managers and researchers to study this problem in order to reduce the psychogenic impact of professional activity on the relevant specialists. As a result of the search for the influence of certain professional situations on the physical and psychological health of a specialist, many theories, models, and approaches to explaining the essence of professional stress have appeared. But, despite their large number, a single concept has not yet been adopted that could explain the versatility of this rather complex phenomenon [24].

The influence of stress on professional results, as evidenced by the studies of V.I. Evdokimov, depends on various professional situations in which the specialist is located. This may be a busy work schedule, fear of losing a job, the complexity of the task, relationships with management, colleagues, etc. In general, this determines the nature of the stressor, the situational factor in the occurrence of stress. A significant factor is also such a factor as the correspondence of the professional training of a specialist to the performed professional activity, the consequence of which may be a change of profession. The named factor can be attributed to situational determinants, as the fact of the presence of a change of profession in the career of an employee. [eleven].

As O.N. Polyakov, today there is no single definition of occupational stress. In this regard, scientific sources use concepts based on different approaches. So, among the most popular, the following generalized definitions can be distinguished: the emotional state of the subject mediated by the inability to realize their significant aspirations, taking into account intrapersonal resources; physiological response to socio-psychological stimuli; neuropsychic overstrain caused by heavy-duty exposure; disturbance of peace that occurs as a reaction to a

certain situation or activity, both external and internal; behavioral response to socio-psychological stimuli [26].

According to N.E. Vodopyanova, the emergence of professional stress is due to the mismatch between the requirements of the environment and the individual himself, the mismatch between what a specific professional situation requires and what a specialist who has a certain level of preparedness can do in this situation. However, the corresponding situation for one individual may be stressful, but not for another. It depends on how this or that specialist evaluates the situation from the position of a threat to himself. For the same individual, one situation at certain periods of time may be perceived as stressful, and in another case - not cause discomfort. This is due to changes in both the physiological state and the psychological status of the specialist [7].

After the theoretical analysis of the problem of occupational stress, S.S. Kuznetsov came to the conclusion that the phenomenon under study is most often understood as such a negative mental state, which is associated with the characteristics and requirements of professional activity. The author, based on various studies, identifies the following levels of analysis of this condition: the first level, within which problems arise in the performance of functional duties by the relevant specialist. They may be associated with the specifics of a particular professional activity; the second level, within which problems arise in the absence of a role balance between the professional and personal spheres. In this aspect, the researcher cites such indicators as role overload, role deficiency, fuzzy role definition, role conflicts; the third level, within which the problems that arise are due to a rather low level of satisfaction in the need-motivational sphere in the process of performing the relevant functions and emotional attitude to professional activity. In this aspect, the researcher gives such an indicator as job satisfaction / dissatisfaction [17].

According to S.B. Malykh, in modern psychological literature, there is often an understanding of stress as a non-specific reaction of the body in response to the increased demands of the environment. In this aspect, requirements are understood as all influences that lead to a change in the activity of the organism. The concept of "non-specific" is due to the fact that the individual's body reacts to any event, as a rule, stereotypically, with the same biochemical changes, and during stress these reactions differ from the norm. In the psychological structure of mental tension, a special role belongs to motivational and emotional components [21].

According to A.S. Kuznetsov, Zakatova A.N. and others, in modern psychological science, the concept of a stressor is understood as any external or internal stimuli that cause excitement or tension in the body. The concept of a stressor is used to distinguish the impact of an event from the consequences that were recorded in the form of an altered physiological and mental state relative to the norm. Stressors are distinguished by the time required for readaptation (from minutes to years). Depending on the combination of these criteria, researchers distinguish such types of stressors as: daily difficulties, i.e. troubles or microstressors; critical life events, i.e. macrostressors; chronic stressors, i.e. diseases [13,18].

To daily difficulties (microstressors) the authors refer to daily stressful life events that cause a violation of well-being. Also under microstressors, daily stressors understand such episodes of everyday experiences and behavior that bring complications and require unusual adaptation. This category of stressors includes problems that are expressed in dissatisfaction with oneself, one's appearance, one's health, one's environment, the quality of

communication, etc. Critical life situations (macrostressors) are situations that, as a rule, meet three main criteria: can be clearly localized in time and space, which distinguishes them from chronic stressors; they require a qualitative reorganization in the human-environment system, which is how they differ from temporary, transitional adaptation; they are accompanied by sustained affective reactions.

In critical life situations, higher energy costs and more time for adaptation are required than is necessary under the action of microstressors.

The main criterion for the concept of a chronic stressor is the duration of the stressor, i.e. these are events that last a long time, are constantly repeated and have a high negative impact. These can be both stress in the family, long-term illnesses, and chronic stress at work, etc. [13, 18].

IN AND. Rozov, T.N. Patrakhina, A.V. Pavlova et al., analyzing modern studies of stress, came to the conclusion that there are several following areas in which the problem of stress is being actively developed: psychophysiological; socio-psychological; individual psychological; professional.

Positive in these studies is their relatively narrow specialization, in-depth study of stress in certain areas of human life. However, this approach can also be considered as having a number of disadvantages, such as the lack of integration, generalization, and integrity in the study of stress. In this case, researchers do not take into account the fact that stress, in the modern understanding, comes as a complex phenomenon that is realized at all levels of the life of the body and the human psyche, and scientific abstraction in the study of its individual manifestations, as a rule, causes impoverishment. general picture of stress [25, 29].

According to L.N. Artamonova, M.A. Single stressors, acting on receptors, include evaluation processes, which, depending on individual experience, individual psychological characteristics, are perceived as positive or negative factors. It is thanks to cognitive processes that stress develops and brings a detrimental effect or is resolved at the stage of meeting with a stressor and does not cause negative changes. Among the main personality characteristics that play an important role in the development of stress, the authors distinguish the following: emotional reactivity - a property of temperament that characterizes the rate of occurrence of emotional arousal. A high level of reactivity increases the risk of occupational stress; neuroticism - a property of temperament, which characterizes the rate of occurrence of nervous excitation. A high level of neuroticism increases the risk of occupational stress; endurance - the conviction and ability to control the events of one's own life and influence them. High endurance softens the impact of stressors, and accordingly, increases stress resistance; locus of control - the tendency of a person to explain the occurrence of significant events in his personal life by external causes or internal, his own efforts. Typically, professionals with an internal locus of control are more resilient to stress; negative affectivity - a person with a pronounced such characteristic tends to feel unhappy and dissatisfied with life in general. In part, she focuses her attention on all the negative aspects of her own life. High levels of negative affectivity are positively correlated with high rates of occupational stress; self-esteem - reflects the attitude towards oneself. The results of research convincingly prove that people with a developed sense of self-esteem are more stress-resistant; self-efficacy is the confidence of a professional that he will solve the problem in an adequate way. Specialists endowed with this quality are more resistant to psychological stress; tolerance to situations of uncertainty - the tendency of an individual to react in a

frustrating way to complex situations. According to research results, low tolerance, i.e. the rapid onset of a state of frustration, positively correlated with a high level of stress; gender characteristics - according to modern research, there are several diverse data. As a rule, women are more likely to complain about the stressfulness of life than men and experience more of the consequences of stress, such as headaches, loss of appetite, and sleep disturbance. However, men are four times more likely to die from cardiovascular disease. But it is still unknown what exactly determines the response to tension (sex, gender or difference in environmental stimuli) [3, 23].

N.V. Samoukina, considering various stress factors, gives the simplest and most consistent classification based on the presentation of G. Lazarus. This classification divides stimuli into physical and psychological stressors, both actual and perceived.

As part of a more extended classification, the author identifies stressors, divided into: uncontrollable, i.e. stressors that are not subordinate to us; controlled, i.e. stressors that can be controlled.

G.G. Arakelov, as the main cause of stress, highlights the impact of stimuli that cause anxiety in most people and leads to a number of physiological, psychological and behavioral reactions. In this case, the interpretation of the situation as stressful is largely determined by the individual-personal characteristics of the person. The author found that the same situation is perceived by different people as stressful or as neutral, depending on the presence or absence of specific personality traits. It is personal characteristics that primarily determine the forms of response to stress and the likely negative consequences of stressful conditions. This can be clearly confirmed by those studies that reveal the relationship between individual character traits and the occurrence of various somatic diseases [2].

A.S. Kleshchenogov, considering some classifications of factors that determine stressful conditions in a person, gives several examples. So, some researchers refer to the main factors that determine the nature of a person's stress reaction, self-regulation, sensitivity to a stressor, stability, while others associate the occurrence of emotional tension with certain character traits and typological features of the nervous system: low emotional stability; belonging to a weak type of nervous system; low mobility of the main nervous processes; pronounced weakness of inhibitory processes; various negative functional reactions and conditions after various diseases [14].

W.V. Vodopyanov, based on the results of his own theoretical analysis, notes that anti-stress, emotional stability is directly related to neuroticism and anxiety. The author notes that under conditions of chronic stress, anxiety develops in people with any type of nervous system, i.e. under the influence of emotionally intense activity, high personal anxiety can become a permanent feature. This personal characteristic has a particularly negative effect in various communications, since an anxious person cannot create a positive emotional mood, negatively influencing others. Affects the personal tendency to develop stress and such quality as aggressiveness. In addition, according to the author, in modern studies, self-esteem is often associated with the development of stressful conditions. According to the results of the analysis, it was found that an increase in self-esteem in a group of various professionals who achieve high results is positively associated with stress resistance, while workers with a low level of skill have an increase in the degree of stress propensity. Based on the above data, the author concludes that adequate self-esteem increases stress resistance. The researcher also highlights the relationship between a person's stress resistance and his locus of control, i.e.

with the growth of the internal locus of control, the specialist copes better with the stressors of professional activity [8].

Research conducted by N.V. Evdokimov point to the ambiguity of the influence of stress on the mental processes of a person. Thus, there are data on the activation of mental processes, regardless of the phase of stress. In particular, there is an improvement in the volume of perception, the level of sensations, the speed of memorization, the stability of attention, the speed of thinking, and communicative activity. In some individuals, as a result of stress, an integrative or differentiated understanding of information is enhanced. Both types of stress activation in their essence act as adaptive-protective reactions and are aimed at mastering the situation and achieving control [10]. At the same time, according to the studies of S. Gremling, S. Auerbach and others, stress negatively affects mental processes. Thus, the authors note a decrease and loss of hearing, speech impairment, erasure of the memory of past experience, or even fragmentary amnesia [9].

N.N. Ravochkin notes that stress is a way to achieve (acquire) the body's resistance when exposed to a harmful factor. It relies on various mechanisms, depending on the complexity of the structural and functional organization of the biosystem. The researcher also emphasizes that stress is a form of anticipatory reflection of reality, thanks to which the body avoids the damaging effect of the stimulus until the changes caused by it become irreversible. That is, non-specific reactions are of a leading nature, and this ensures the reliability of the adaptive behavior of the biosystem in rapidly changing conditions of existence. This view is a positive assessment of stress and its place in the life of the body [27].

T.I. Abolina believes that the interpretation of a positive assessment of stress is possible only if it is identified with mental stress. Researchers distinguish between these concepts and define stress as a process that always leads to one or another mental disorder, i.e. stress, as a rule, can be characterized as a harmful phenomenon that causes significant harm to the body, can act as the main cause of various diseases [1].

S.S. Rakityanskaya characterizes the body's stress response to external stimuli as a complex of mental and somatic disorders that develop as a result of significant or repeated emotional stresses that exceed the capabilities of mental adaptation. The most common and common symptoms of stress are headache, stomach pain, chest tightness, lower back pain, heaviness, tension at the base of the neck, and chronic constipation. Other symptoms are also possible: insomnia; decrease in working capacity; inability to fully concentrate; irritability; rupture or complication of relations with loved ones; lethargy, inertia, general decline in life, etc.

Under the influence of stress, people become depressed, lose sleep, become uncommunicative, irritable, frivolous, restless, apathetic. In addition to these symptoms, stress is the cause of many somatic diseases. For example, protracted, stereotypically repetitive negative emotions lead to the development of specific bodily disorders - psychosomatic diseases [28].

Analysis of modern research conducted by I.U. Hereditary showed that stress reduces the efficiency of the immune system by reducing T-lymphocytes. As a result, it becomes more likely to develop allergic reactions, asthma attacks and even cancer. In conditions of chronic emotional activity, the development of protracted disorders is possible. Those. Stress contributes to many diseases. It has been established that occupational stress can cause disorders of cardiovascular functions, including persistent arterial hypertension, myocardial

infarction, sclerosis of the coronary vessels, angina pectoris; ischemic heart disease. In addition, stress contributes to such diseases of the gastrointestinal tract as peptic ulcer of the stomach and duodenum. Stress also increases muscle tension and muscle immobilization, which is considered the main cause of headache, back pain, neck and shoulder pain. According to the author, all the information about the stresses experienced by a person remains in the muscles. Moreover, daily freezing of emotions, the load of which settles in the body in the form of areas of muscle tension - painful muscle indurations or bodily equivalents of emotions, leads to the gradual formation of a muscle shell [22].

T.V. Zaichikova believes that stress can indeed cause a large number of different negative consequences. At the same time, according to the author, many scientists do not unambiguously attribute stress to a negative or positive phenomenon in human life, due to various conditions that determine the nature of stress reactions. According to this approach, stress can be considered both positive and negative for the body of various kinds of reactions. Those. distinguish between positive and negative stress. Almost any professional activity can cause significant stress without causing any harm. As a rule, a combination of situational overstrain and limited cognitive and emotional capabilities leads to a disease [12].

According to I.O. Kotenev, an important parameter for the classification of stress is the time factor. Long-term exposure to stress is especially dangerous. For example, in ten to fifteen years of work in extreme conditions, the body of an individual wears out as if he had experienced a severe heart attack. It has been established that in a chronic stressful situation, there is a violation of mental adaptation, which develops in accordance with four stages, which are considered as successive stages of a mental crisis. And, on the contrary, a strong short-term stress activates a specialist, as if shakes it off, increasing the adaptive potential.

Another factor for distinguishing types of stress, according to the researcher, is the age criterion. Accordingly, adult and children's stresses are distinguished. In addition, there is a difference between the perception and response to stress in adulthood and old age. Despite the fact that age is one of the main factors in determining the stress response, in this respect it is still not well understood [15].

L.V. Kulikov draws attention to the peculiarities of the duration of stress. If short-term stress has a positive effect on the body, mobilizing it, then long-term stress has an unfavorable effect, destroying it. The type of stress also has a significant impact on the nature of the stress response and the likely negative consequences. It is known that psychological stress is much more likely than stress from excessive muscular work (physical stress) to lead to disease. Among the factors that determine the modality of stress - the emotionally positive or negative nature of stress, there are: the possibility of choice; degree of control over the situation; the possibility of predicting or preventing adverse consequences [16].

Conclusion. Thus, based on the foregoing, it seems appropriate to conclude that today, despite the lack of a unified definition of the concept under study, its active use in various studies is observed. Occupational stress is considered as the main generic concept that generalizes a fairly wide range of terms: work stress; work stress; work stress; organizational stress, etc. They, as a rule, denote the mental states of the personality of the subject of labor that arise in the process of professional activity, its specific conditions. At the same time, most modern approaches to the study of occupational stress are closely related to the psychology of occupational health, the effectiveness of the performance of professional activities,

optimization of the management process, interpersonal relationships, establishing proper interaction, etc.

References:

1. Аболина Т.И. К проблеме психологического стресса // Психология спортивной деятельности. - Изд-во Казанского университета. - 2001. - С. 123-129.
2. Аракелов Г.Г. Стресс и его механизмы // Вестник МГУ. Сер. Психология. - 2001. - №3. - С. 71-78.
3. Артамонова Л.Н. Организационный стресс у сотрудников банка / Л.Н. Артамонова, А.Б. Леонова // Вестник МГУ. Серия 14. Психология - 2009. - № 1. С. 28-42.
4. Баймуратов Т.Р., Еникеева А.М., Кутдусова Э.Д., Насретдинова Л.М., Хусаенова А.А. Особенности общения медработников и пациентов, перенёвших инсульт // Молодой ученый. - 2019. - №7. - С. 129-131.
5. Бодров В.А. Профессиональный стресс: возникновение, развитие и преодоление / В.А. Бодров. - М.: Наука, 2010. - 162 с.
6. Ванковский А.Н. Профессиональный стресс и функциональные состояния. / Ред. Дикая Л.Г., Занковский А.Н. - М.: Наука, 2012. - 159 с.
7. Водопьянова Н.Е. Профессиональный стресс: сущность, основные причины возникновения, последствия. - М., 2009. - 98 с.
8. Водопьянов У.В. Стресс в современных условиях. - М.: Наука, 2010. - 140 с.
9. Гремлинг С., Ауэрбах С. Практикум по управлению стрессом. - Спб.: Питер, 2002. - 240 с.
10. Евдокимов Н.В. Влияние стресса на психические процессы человека. // Социальная психология и общество. - 2011. - № 7 - С. 123-130.
11. Евдокимов В.И. Стресс и профессиональная деятельность. М., 2011. - 123 с.
12. Зайчикова Т.В. Стресс в профессиональной деятельности // Актуальные проблемы психологии, Том 1.: Социальная психология. Психология управления. Организационная психология. - Киев: Институт психологии им. С. Костюка АПН Украины, 2007. - Ч.5. - С. 160-165.
13. Закатова А.Н. Стресс замедленного действия // Новый персонал. -2010. -№6. - 34-38 с.46
14. Клещеногов А.С. Факторы детерминирующие стрессовые состояния человека. // Современная психология. - 2008. - №6. - С. 67-75.55
15. Котенев И.О. Стресс в профессиональной деятельности. - М.: АУ МВД России, 2004. - 67 с.
16. Куликов Л.В. Виды трудового стресса // Психология состояний. Хрестоматия / Под ред. Прохорова А.В. - М.: Речь, 2004. - С. 128-144.
17. Кузнецов С.С. Психология профессионального стресса - М.: Эксмо, 2006. - 104 с.
18. Кузнецов А.С. Признаки стресса в поведении человека // Молодой ученый. - 2019. - №51. - С. 462-464.
19. Леонова А.Б. Комплексная стратегия анализа стресса: от диагностики к профилактике и коррекции. Психологический журнал, 2004, Т. 25, - С. 75-85.
20. Леонова А.Б. Основные подходы к изучению профессионального стресса // Вестник психосоциальной и коррекционно-реабилитационной работы. - 2001. - № 11. - С. 2-16.

- 21.Kuchkarova, O. (2021). МАКТАБГАЧНА YOSHDAGI BOLALARNI КИТОВ O'QISHGA QIZIQTIRISHDA PSIXOLOGIYANING O'RNI. Academic research in educational sciences, 2(4).
- 22.Umirzaqovna, M. D. FACETED PERSONALITIES OF DETERMINANTS OF PROFESSIONAL STRESS IN DOCTORS OF GENERAL PRACTICE.
- 23.Мамадиярова, Д. У. (2020). ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ ВЛИЯНИЯ ПРОГРАММЫ ТРЕНИНГОВЫХ ЗАНЯТИЙ ПО ПРОФИЛАКТИКЕ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНОГО СТРЕССА У БУДУЩИХ ВРАЧЕЙ ОБЩЕЙ ПРАКТИКИ. Современное образование (Узбекистан), (8 (93)), 30-37.
- 24.Мамадиярова, Д. У. (2020). УРОВНИ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНОГО СТРЕССА У ВРАЧЕЙ ОБЩЕЙ ПРАКТИКИ. In Сборники конференций НИЦ Социосфера (No. 18, pp. 14-17). Vedecko vydavatelske centrum Sociosfera-CZ sro.
- 25.Мамадиярова, Д. У. (2020). СТРУКТУРНАЯ МОДЕЛЬ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНОГО СТРЕССА ВРАЧЕЙ ОБЩЕЙ ПРАКТИКИ. In СОВРЕМЕННАЯ ПСИХОЛОГИЯ И ПЕДАГОГИКА: ПРОБЛЕМЫ И РЕШЕНИЯ (pp. 81-86).
- 26.IIhomjonova, S. T., & Ochilova, F. B. (2022, March). BURNOUT SYNDROME AS A PSYCHOLOGICAL PROBLEM. In E Conference Zone (pp. 41-42).
- 27.Xudoynazarovna, Q. O. (2022). Technology Of Development Of Social Activity Of Female Pedagogues In The Conditions Of The New Renaissance. Journal of Positive School Psychology, 6(9), 4469-4471.
- 28.Qurbonovich, U. U. (2022). Factors Of Development Of Teacher's Spiritual Image. Journal of Positive School Psychology, 6(9), 4472-4475.
- 29.Xudoynazarovna, Q. O. (2022). The Role of Innovative Technologies in the Quality Organization of the Educational Process of Female Teachers. Vital Annex: International Journal of Novel Research in Advanced Sciences, 1(6), 133-136.
- 30.Xudoynazarovna, Q. O., & Alisher o'g'li, H. A. (2022). SOCIO-PEDAGOGICAL MATERIAL TO ENSURE THE CONTINUITY OF FAMILY, NEIGHBORHOOD AND EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTION IN THE FORMATION OF SPIRITUAL AND MORAL VIRTUES OF STUDENTS. Modern Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities, 4, 342-344.
- 31.Xudoynazarovna, Q. O. (2022). INCREASING SOCIAL AND POLITICAL ACTIVITY OF WOMEN IN OUR COUNTRY. TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI, 2(12), 249-255.
- 32.Norbo'tayev F. M., Sh A. F. THE ROLE, ESSENCE AND CRITERIA OF SOCIAL COMPENSATION IN STUDENTS //Spectrum Journal of Innovation, Reforms and Development. – 2022. – T. 4. – С. 177-181.

